

Civil and Military Synergism at Soekarno–Hatta International Airport in Preventing the Transmission of Covid–19

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ABSTRACT: International Airport is a public service facility that provides transportation services both domestic and international. Dealing with Covid-19 as non-natural disasters requires collaboration between civilian and military actors where the use of the military as a form of non-war operations and the use of "idle capacity" in peacetime. This research was conducted using a qualitative method with an exploratory approach where the subject of this research are the actors involved in the prevention of Covid-19 transmission at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport and the focal point of the UN CM Coord. The findings of this study revealed that the coordination between civil-military was evidenced by the joint efforts of the KOMBATA (Komunitas Bandara Internasional Soekarno-Hatta) by running various programs: Biosafety Management System, Biosecurity Management System, Airport Health Center, Vaccination Center, and Workforce Protection, to strengthen health protocols and protect the citizens and operational operators. In terms of coordination between civil and military, there are 3 important elements: information sharing, task division, and planning. In the process, obstacles appeared in the sharing information between institutions and institutions, as well as institutions and travelers both domestically and internationally, so that it became a challenge in implementing protocols

KEYWORDS- Covid-19, Civil and Military Coordination, Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, Synergism

I. INTRODUCTION

More than a year Covid-19 attacks all countries in the world without mercy. After the World Health Organization declared Coronavirus Disease 2019 a global pandemic on March 11, 2020, President Joko Widodo then declared the spread of the Covid-19 outbreak a national disaster. The emergency status comes into effect as of April 13, 2020. The determination of the spread of the Covid-19 virus as a disaster is stated in Presidential Decree (Keppres) No. 12 of 2020 concerning Determination of Non-Natural Disasters. Non-Natural Disasters are disasters caused by non-natural events or series of events, which include failure of technology, failure of modernization, epidemics, and disease outbreaks. The spread of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) is referred to as a National Disaster because of its widespread impact throughout Indonesia and even the world.

Living side by side with Covid-19, when viewed from a disaster perspective, can be started with pre-disaster activities which include development planning, disaster risk analysis (in this case Covid-19), disaster risk reduction, disaster management planning, education and training. From a policy perspective, a series of policies to support coexistence with a pandemic is definitely needed so that, for example, development planning takes disaster risk aspects into consideration (iap2.or.id). Likewise in a number of places where public service

activities are possible. Government policies to prevent the spread of Covid-19 transmission will certainly have an impact on the standards of public services operated by service providers. Improving the standard of public services will be one of the efforts to prevent the spread of the Covid-19 virus. Control and prevention of Covid-19 transmission in public service facilities, in this case an important point that must be prioritized is the Health protocol.

The International Airport is one of public service with various transportation activities both domestically and abroad. The large number of citizens who make departures and arrivals in large numbers and interactions that are not monitored can have great potential as carriers of Covid-19. Soekarno-Hatta International Airport Tangerang as an international airport is one of the transit and landing places for foreign nationals as well as the departure place for Indonesian citizens abroad, which according to data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) of Tangerang City in 2020 was recorded based on data from the Indonesian Transportation Service in 2017. 2020 statistical data for international passengers shows 1,542,512 arrivals and 1,517,881 departures (tangerangkota.bps.go.id). Data on population movements, both coming and going out of Indonesia, creates the possibility of transmission or transfer of viral pathogens, if an infected foreign country brings the pathogen to an uninfected country. In this case, a number of stakeholders who work at the airport must be alert in terms of handling the prevention of transmission of the Covid-19 virus.

To protect the public traveling and potentially infected at airports and in air transportation systems may have considerable policy implications for aviation security such as the TSA (Transportation Security Administration). However, in the case of the previous MERS-CoV pandemic, the administrative inspection process took quite a long time, so prospective passengers at the airport are encouraged to arrive much earlier so that there is no overcrowding at the inspection site and still prioritize health protocols (Reza, 2016:vii). Likewise with the Covid-19 pandemic, a number of administrative requirements and provisions in order to support health protocols are non-negotiable and must be obeyed together because this is what we can use to control the spread of Covid-19 where in this case the community also takes role in preventing the spread of Covid-19 which also collaborates with the role of aviation security such as risk-based screening for symptoms of infectious diseases at airports. Other possible roles include measures to isolate or quarantine sick passengers and the use of passenger facilities and other travel records to track and reduce the spread of disease in identifying and quarantining individuals potentially exposed to infectious diseases during flights. In the fight against a pandemic that is becoming increasingly dangerous with the new variant of the corona virus, at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, Tangerang, the flight passenger travel rules will be updated starting March 2021. The change in the flight rules for airplane passengers is to prevent the spread of the mutation of the corona virus that was mutated in the UK. , B.1.1.7 (kontan.co.id).

Handling Covid-19 requires coordination between civilian and military actors. In some cases of disasters, coordination between civilian and military actors has been shown to increase effectiveness in disaster management. Coordination between civilians and the military at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport is evidenced by the joint efforts of the KOMBATA unit (Soekarno-Hatta International Airport Community) in terms of preventing the transmission of Covid-19. KOMBATA consists of PT Angkasa Pura II, Immigration, Police, Garuda Indonesia, Customs, Kodim, Quarantine, Airport Authority, Port Health Office, Task Force, Airport Police, to cleaning service, security and tenants at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport. (kkpsoetta.com). Although Soekarno-Hatta International Airport is a special airport for civil aviation, the presence of the TNI at the airport is a manifestation of the TNI's responsibility, especially the Air Force in carrying out the task of air defense security from all fields of interference, threats, and even terror in aviation cases. This is regulated in Article 10 of the TNI Law, which is implemented in the formation of the Special Task Force for International Airport Security (SatgasAksus Pam Bandara) (p2k.unkris.ac.id). Especially in a pandemic situation, the military presence contributes to maintaining national security from the dangers of Covid-19 transmission. Until now, Soekarno-Hatta International Airport still sets high standards for airport health protocols.

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II. THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1. National Security Theory

Security or security comes from the Latin *securus* which has the meaning of being free from danger, fear and threat. Security itself is viewed from two approaches, which have the traditional sense of security which is defined as the security of a country that can be intervened by military forces from other countries and must be protected by that country with its military power. In this approach, the state is both subject and object in creating security. Furthermore, the second approach is non-traditional security which is defined as security that is focused on the security needs of non-state actors (A'raf, 2015: 28-29).

In the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution, it has been mandated that the national goal of the state is to protect the entire Indonesian nation and to promote general welfare, educate the nation's life and participate in implementing world order based on independence, eternal peace and social justice. Henceforth, these objectives are stated in the Defense White Paper which also explains that the national interest of a country will be used as a reference in the formulation and determination of a grand strategy or national security strategy. Stable national security is fundamental to the smooth implementation of national development in order to realize national goals.

Within that framework, national security is a dynamic national interest (Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia, 2015: 27). The development of military and non-military defense institutions is carried out in order to realize an integrated power in the management of national defense through strengthening and rearranging as well as institutional restructuring.

2.2. Disaster Management Theory

In Law No. 24/2007 concerning Disaster Management, disaster is defined as an event or series of events caused by nature, humans and/or both that threaten and disrupt people's lives and livelihoods caused, both by natural factors and/or non-natural factors as well as human factors, resulting in the emergence of human casualties, environmental damage, property losses, and psychological impacts. Disasters are divided into 3 types, namely natural disasters, non-natural disasters, and social disasters. According to Oxfam Indonesia (2012) disaster is defined as a phenomenon that occurs as a result of the collectivity of the hazard components that affect natural and environmental conditions and how the level of vulnerability and capacity of a community in managing threats. Meanwhile, according to the United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction or UN-ISDR (2009: 9), a disaster is defined as a serious disruption to the functioning of a society, causing widespread harm to human life from a material, economic or environmental point of view and which exceeds the ability of the community concerned to cope using their own resources.

From some of the definitions above, the essence of Disaster Management Theory can be drawn:

- a. Disasters are events that result in victims of human suffering, loss of property, environmental damage, damage to infrastructure and public facilities and cause disturbances to the way of life and livelihoods.
- b. Disaster management includes 3 phases, namely pre-disaster, emergency response, and post-disaster phases.
- c. An understanding of the disaster aspect also includes several disaster parameters such as hazard, vulnerability, and risk.

2.3. Sinergism Theory

Synergism comes from the word synergy. According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (2005), synergy means joint activities or operations. Therefore, synergism in development means the integration of various elements of development that can produce better and larger outputs. According to the theory of synergism (James A. F. Stoner and Charles Wankel, 1986), the best level of cooperation is synergistic, namely high cooperation, mutual trust, and integration so as to produce an output that is greater than the sum of the outputs of each party.

Najiyati and Rahmat (2011), define synergy as a combination or combination of elements or parts that can produce better and greater output. So synergy can be understood as a joint operation or a combination of elements to produce a better output. Synergism can be built in two ways, there are:

- a. Communications
Sofyandi and Garniwa (2007), the notion of communication can be divided into two parts:
 - 1) The notion of source-oriented communication states that, communication is an activity by which a person (source) actually transfers stimuli in order to get a response.
 - 2) Understanding of receiver-oriented communication views that communication as all activities in which a person (receiver) responds to a stimulus or stimuli.
- b. Coordination

Besides the existence of communication in creating synergies also requires coordination. Communication cannot stand alone without coordination as stated by Hasan that coordination is needed in communication (2005: 18).

2.4. Pandemic Theory

A pandemic is a disease outbreak that spreads very quickly to people and occurs in almost all regions of the world, covers a very wide range, and crosses international boundaries (Masrul, 2020). Corona viruses are a large family of viruses that cause disease in humans and animals. In humans, it usually causes respiratory tract infections, ranging from the common cold to serious illnesses such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS).

A new type of coronavirus found in humans since an extraordinary event appeared in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, was later named Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-COV2), and caused Coronavirus Disease-2019 (COVID-19). The World Health Organization (WHO) has determined that the corona virus or commonly referred to as COVID 19 has become a pandemic because this virus has spread to various countries and has even gone global. WHO defines a pandemic as a condition of the world's population and the potential to cause falls and illness. A pandemic is an epidemic that spreads simultaneously everywhere. The COVID-19 pandemic also has an impact on various sectors of life, such as the economy, social and education, to public services.

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that national authorities continue to adopt a risk-based approach when implementing measures related to COVID-19 and international travel while respecting the dignity, human rights and fundamental freedoms of travelers or tourists. This approach should take into account the risks posed by travel for the import and export of cases in the evolving epidemiological context, including the emergence and circulation of viral variants of concern; expansion of COVID-19 vaccination rollout; and lessons learned in responding to a pandemic, including early detection and treatment of cases and the implementation of public health and social measures (WHO, 2021).

2.5. Civil-Military Relations

Regarding civil-military relations, there are various definitions that differ in terms of levels of operation and authority. This approach was put forward by UN-OCHA, where there is Civil Military Cooperation and Civil Military Coordination.

In Civil Military Cooperation, the Department of Peacekeeping Operations (DPKO) defines: the function of military staff that contributes to facilitating the interface between the military and civilian components of an integrated mission, as well as with humanitarian and development actors within the mission, region, in support of the objectives of the United Nations Mission. In the context of UN peacekeeping, this coordination is called "UN-CIMIC". The North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) defines: A shared function consisting of an integral set of capabilities to support the achievement of mission objectives and enable the NATO command to participate effectively in a broad spectrum of civil-military interactions with a variety of non-military actors.

In the explanation above, it can be understood that civil and military relations in the context of CIMIC lead to civil-military interactions with peacekeeping missions by using joint force in which the military actor is the host.

The Humanitarian Civil-Military Coordination (UN-CMCoord or CMCoord) is an important dialogue and interaction between civilian and military actors in humanitarian emergencies that is needed to protect and promote humanitarian principles, avoid competition, minimize inconsistencies and, if necessary, , pursuing a common goal. The basic strategies range from cooperation to coexistence. Coordination is a shared responsibility facilitated by joint liaison and training (OCHA, 2018:55)

In any humanitarian response, dialogue and interaction with all armed actors is an important aspect of humanitarian activity. However, the objectives, strategies and mechanisms will be different. In disasters during peacetime, the focus may be on coordination and appropriate use of FMA (Force Military Assets) to support humanitarian operations. In humanitarian aid operations, coordination between humanitarian actors and the military is essential to protect and promote humanitarian principles, avoid competition, minimize inconsistency and, where necessary, pursue common goals. The need for coordination is further strengthened in a complex and high-risk environment where clear distinctions between humanitarian and military actors are critical to maintaining the civilian character of humanitarian operations. This ensures safe humanitarian access, protection of civilians and the safety of humanitarian aid workers (OCHA, 2018:30)

In any civil-military coordination, humanitarian actors must continue to play the main role in conducting and directing humanitarian activities. The independence of humanitarian action and decision-making must be maintained at both the operational and policy levels at all times. Humanitarian organizations may not carry out their duties on behalf of the military or represent or enforce their policies. Basic requirements such as freedom of movement for humanitarian staff, freedom to exercise independent judgment, freedom to choose staff, freedom to identify aid recipients based on their needs, or the free flow of communication between humanitarian

With the explanation above, the right concept to explain the direction of this research is Civil-Military Coordination (CM-Coord) in which civilian actors are the hosts.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative research method with an exploratory approach. This research was conducted at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, Benda District, Tangerang City. In this study, researchers collect information by means of interviews, observation and documentation. The subjects of this research are the actors involved in preventing the transmission of Covid-19 at Soekarno Hatta International Airport and the focal point for the UN CMCoord. The validity of the data was tested by using credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability tests.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

Soekarno-Hatta International Airport is the gateway for the entry of people from outside the region and abroad. Therefore, Soekarno-Hatta International Airport has special standards to support general health protocols that refer to WHO, including 3M and 3T. 3M and 3T are the main keys to handling Covid-19, where 3M's health protocols include wearing masks, maintaining distance, and washing hands with soap. Meanwhile, the Government continues to implement 3T (Tracing, Testing, Treatment) practices with the support of all levels of society. 3M and 3T are a package of efforts that cannot be separated to break the chain of transmission of COVID-19 (covid.go.id). This also applies at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, where especially at the airport, only testing and screening is carried out as part of tracing which checks whether PCR, antigen, etc. have been tested as administrative completeness. Furthermore, treatment is a form of follow-up such as quarantine for travelers at the airport.

- a. 3M Protocol
 - 1) Wearing a mask

Masks are effective in reducing the risk of exposure/contagion. Without wearing a mask, the risk of transmitting COVID-19 in aerosol form (very small particles that can float in the air) is 40% and in droplet form as much as 30%. However, the risk of transmitting COVID-19 both droplets and aerosols becomes 0% by wearing a mask (Nature Medicine, 2020). The use of masks slowed the spread of COVID-19 cases by 0.9% after 5 days, and slowed by 2% after 3 weeks. Countries that implement mandatory wearing of masks have lower mortality rates. The use of masks slowed the spread of COVID-19 cases by 0.9% after 5 days, and slowed by 2% after 3 weeks. Countries that implement the mandatory use of masks have lower mortality rates (SatgasCovid-19, 2021).

2) Keep your distance & Avoid crowds

We cannot know who has been affected by COVID-19, so it is important for us to stay at home and practice physical distancing. When traveling outside such as shopping or medical needs, we must maintain a safe distance of 2 meters from each other. Maintain a safe distance of 2 meters from other people. Don't shake hands, hold hands, or hug. Avoid being close to anyone and anywhere. Limiting gatherings with other people, such as group activities.

2) Washing Hands With Soap

Hands an important role in the transmission of micro-organisms or microorganisms and easily occur when we do not maintain good hand hygiene. Washing hands is one of the most important steps we can take to avoid getting sick and spreading the virus to others. WHO has established frequent hand washing with soap and water as a precautionary measure to reduce the possibility of spreading the virus. The mechanism of soap in killing germs and removing viruses is based on the mechanism of breaking the viral membrane, simple elution, and entrapment of the virus (Caundhary et al., 2020).

b. 3T

The second protocol is 3T: Testing, Tracing and Treatment. This is not as easy as 3M because it involves other parties, but it must be implemented properly. This approach is designed by identifying COVID-19 cases with health checks through several types of tests for confirmed COVID-19 detection, then tracing people who spend time and are in close contact with them and may be infected, then an approach to self-isolation, so that if infected you can prevent its transmission to others (Rajan et al., 2020).

1) Testing

Important tests are carried out to avoid the potential for transmitting the virus that causes COVID-19 to others and so that a person can get treatment quickly (covid.go.id). Generally, there are three types of COVID-19 tests that are often used to detect whether a person is infected with the SARS-CoV-2 virus or not, including antigen tests (antigen swabs), molecular tests (RNA swabs/PCR), and breath tests (swab tests). Each type of test has a different level of accuracy for detecting COVID-19 infection.

2) Tracing

Investigations need to be carried out as soon as there are confirmed cases. The tracing process is difficult to carry out if the transmission rate occurs quickly and rapidly, so that the focus of the search can be done on household contacts, health workers, and closed places that are at high risk, for example: dormitories, nursing homes, nursing homes. (WHO, 2020)

3) Treatment

If a positive patient has no symptoms, he is required to self-isolate in a facility provided by the government or can self-isolate at home under supervision from the local health center. Meanwhile, positive patients with symptoms are required to isolate themselves in hospitals that have been appointed by the government. If the patient after the test shows a negative result but has symptoms, the patient can self-isolate at home. Self-isolation is carried out to

keep people around us from being infected and to make it easier for health workers to monitor the health of isolated people (Ministry of Health, 2020).

In the standard protocols owned by Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, generally protocols such as 3M and 3T have been implemented with the coordination of all devices at the airport. The standards or special programs from Soekarno-Hatta International Airport include (angkasapura2.co.id):

a. Biosecurity Management System

Biosecurity management is carried out to protect the public from the dangers of Covid (tribunnews.com), with the following programs:

- 1) Physical distancing: the obligation to maintain a distance in every area of the airport.
- 2) Health screening: checking body temperature, checking the results of a rapid test or PCR test.
- 3) Passenger touchless processing: more facilities without touch, for example in elevators, toilets, vehicle parking areas and other areas.
- 4) Facility cleanliness: routine disinfection of all facilities for passengers.
- 5) People protection: mandatory use of personal protective equipment (PPE) such as masks for everyone at the terminal, both travelers and airport staff.

b. Biosafety Management System

Meanwhile, through bio safety management, PT Angkasa Pura II has programs:

- 1) Biohazard Precautions: Efforts to prevent and protect the health of airport service users from the threat of the Covid-19 virus outbreak.
- 2) Environment screening: Keeping the environment clean and healthy, for example the application of good air circulation, the use of UV sterilizers, and in the future the use of plasma clusters and HEPA filters in terminals.
- 3) Testing lab facilities: Soekarno-Hatta International Airport is planned to have laboratory facilities to test travelers for COVID-19.
- 4) Infrastructure sterilization: Disinfection is carried out in every building at the airport.
- 5) Public health assurance: the company's airport has a handling protocol at the airport for those who are indicated to be infected with COVID-19

c. Airport Health Center

The Airport Health Center is operated by competent partners, there are Kimia Farma and Indofarma. The provider of Rapid Test Antigen and PCR services at AHC Terminals 1, 2 and Terminal 3 is PT FarmalabIndoutama (Indofarma) (soekarnohatta-airport.co.id). PT Angkasa Pura II as the manager of Soekarno-Hatta International Airport has the authority to supervise these services so that they remain in accordance with the applicable standard operating procedure (SOP). pandemic. In line with the increasingly reliable Airport Health Center at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, starting Sunday, December 27, PT Angkasa Pura II opened the opportunity for the general public to be able to perform a special COVID-19 test at the Airport Health Center Terminal 1 of Soekarno-Hatta International Airport.

PT Angkasa Pura II continues to supervise services at AHC Soekarno-Hatta International Airport. Sudden inspections (sidak) are also carried out periodically so that the service runs according to the SOP. In addition to ensuring that the test devices used are new and sealed, FarmalabIndoutama officers serving at AHC Soekarno-Hatta International Airport routinely undergo regular Covid-19 examinations/tests. This is to ensure that the HR on duty is in a healthy condition and free from Covid-19.

PT. Angkasa Pura II (Persero) strives for the results of the RT-PCR test conducted at the Airport Health Center at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport to be known more quickly as an effort to support aircraft passengers in fulfilling travel conditions. Based on the coordination of the stakeholders, it was determined that the results of the tests carried out starting October 24, 2021 at the RT-PCR drive thru Airport Health Center service at Terminal 3 can be known within 3 hours or faster than the usual 1x24 to avoid crowded airports. However, for PCR tests carried out at

other points of the Airport Health Center, such as walk-in service and pre-order service at Terminal 3, as well as walk-in service, pre-order service and drive thru service at Terminal 2, the results can still be known 1x24 hours.

d. Vaccination Center

In order to succeed President Jokowi's national vaccination target, Soekarno-Hatta International Airport also participated by opening a vaccination center. This is evidenced by the stage I vaccination attack at Arrival Terminal 1 A of Soekarno-Hatta International Airport on July 9, 2021 and the stage II vaccination attack, at Arrival Terminal 1 A of Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, Cengkareng, Tangerang, Monday, August 9, 2021 ago (tribunnews.com). This vaccination attack continues to be carried out based on an assessment where crucial places, such as airports are places with the potential for the spread of the Covid-19 virus, so that they are carried out to increase herd immunity for airport stakeholders.

e. Workforce Protection

Workforce Protection which has been carried out since March 2020 to protect employees including operational and service personnel at the airport. The Workforce Protection programs include:

- 1) Operational pattern adjustment: Normal Operation, Slow Down Operation, Minimum Operation 1 and 2
- 2) Mandatory use of PPE: Level 1 PPE, Level 2 PPE, up to Level 3 PPE that uses a complete hazmat
- 3) Tracing, tracking and testing: PT Angkasa Pura II has an internal iPerform application to perform tracing and tracking management for all employees. Employees, especially airport operational and service personnel, also conduct regular rapid tests
- 4) Service adjustments: Face-to-face customer service is abolished, replaced with VICA (virtual customer assistant) Dilakukan pemeriksaan suhu tubuh sebelum personel bertugas

Workforce Protection is an internal regulation to protect employees in the midst of this pandemic. Workforce Protection sees it from various sides, namely by adjusting operational patterns or reducing operating hours, airport personnel have more time to stay at home but airport operations can still run smoothly. Personnel are also equipped with PPE ranging from level 1 to level 3 which is adapted to the situation and function of the personnel.

In handling Covid-19, all actors, both government and non-government, have a responsibility to assist in handling Covid-19, including in terms of policy. For example, UN-OCHA in the humanitarian field, which advocates for a response plan with the premise that this pandemic will have multiple (multiple) impacts on all sectors, some of which have been carried out by the ministry/institution that handles the matter. In addition, military involvement is also linked in helping to deal with this problem. This is in accordance with the Indonesian regime where for disaster management, the TNI is always involved which is part of OMSP (Military Operations Other Than War). So in operations in the field, it is necessary to have actors who synergize with each other, both civil and military apparatus. Synergism means that the combined activities usually have a greater influence than the total amount of their individual effects or one by one.

The key elements of coordination in complex disasters and emergencies are Information sharing, Task division, and Planning. The scope and modus operandi of these key elements will change depending on the context and the opponent (in this case the opponent or enemy is Covid-19)

a. Information sharing

Minimal information should always be exchanged, to increase mutual awareness. This may include information sharing and situational analysis, for example on security, threats and displacement relevant to humanitarian assistance and PoC. Willingness to share information will be based on trust and clear communication by humanitarian actors about what information they need and to for what purpose, and how the information will be used.

In the case at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, the sharing of information is one of the problems, in which the relevant parties or institutions do not inform the SOPs or strict rules in Indonesia to travellers (domestic and international) as well as all airlines or transportation agents. This sometimes becomes an obstacle for stakeholders who have to re-filter the entry of travelers from or arriving at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport.

b. Task division

In a context where the activities of humanitarian and military actors can (partially) complement each other, a division of labor is necessary. This occurs mostly in peacetime disasters, but can also occur in complex emergencies (eg in PoC).

At the beginning of the pandemic, based on the experience of resource person Jorry S. Koloay who was the former chairman of the Covid-19 Task Force at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport, he explained that there are several parties who have their own sectoral egos, where one party wants to stand out more or feel more superior. However, along with the ongoing coordination, communication and evaluation, it is able to improve the situation so that the stakeholders work according to their portions..

c. Planning

It is common practice that military support for humanitarian operations is sometimes limited to infrastructure support. Potential negative implications should always be thoroughly analyzed by humanitarian actors.

- 1) General operational overview: Who does what, where, and until when is very important to avoid duplication or work that is not in accordance with the portion.
- 2) Cost planning for operational activities handling Covid-19 at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport.

With sufficient information, it can reduce or avoid unwanted conflicts and challenges in the field, so that civilian and military actors remain in good synergy. With the Covid-19 national disaster condition, we can see that an important point in the synergy of civil and military apparatuses, especially at airports, is to unite information, especially SOPs from each institution/agencies, which can create work harmony during a pandemic like this. At the beginning of the pandemic, it is sometimes seen that each party wants to be seen as dominant or a sectoral ego where one party wants to stand out or feel more authority so that it is less integrated. But now it's more solid because::

- a. Weekly evaluation is always carried out in the form of finding the root of the problem and accommodating complaints from passengers and other officers in carrying out their duties in the field
- b. From this evaluation, a mutually agreed SOP is used
- c. Follow up on existing complaints or evaluations
- d. Each institution can understand and accept and complement each other regarding their respective duties and authorities.

The synergy between the civil and military apparatus has made it one of the 38 best airports in the world based on the Skytrax Awards. This is because:

- a. Mechanisms and services are fast and well served, and well recorded
- b. Using an electronic system
- c. The role of each officer in the field and stakeholders is in accordance with their portion, namely KOMBATA (Soekarno-Hatta International Airport Community) which consists of the TNI, Polri, KKP, Immigration, to Security Guard, Tenant Employees and Cleaning Service).

V. CONCLUSION

The International Airport is one of the places of public service with various transportation activities both domestically and abroad. The large number of citizens who make departures or arrivals in large numbers and interactions that are not monitored can have great potential as carriers of Covid-19. Soekarno-Hatta International Airport Tangerang as an international airport is one of the transit and landing places for foreign nationals as well as the departure point for Indonesian citizens abroad and one of the busiest airports in Indonesia. Therefore, living in tandem with the pandemic requires policymakers to promote and strengthen protocols in public facilities, especially at airports.

From this research, the researcher can draw 2 conclusions from the 2 research questions that the researcher has studied in depth.

1. Implementation of Health Protocols at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport in Prevention of Covid-19 Transmission

Soekarno-Hatta International Airport has special standards to support general health protocols that refer to WHO, including 3M and 3T. 3M and 3T are the main keys to handling Covid-19, where 3M's health protocols are wearing masks, maintaining distance, and washing hands with soap. Meanwhile, the government continues to carry out 3T (Tracing, Testing, Treatment) practices with the support of all levels of society. 3M and 3T are a package of efforts that cannot be separated to break the chain of transmission of COVID-19. Furthermore, to protect security in a broad spectrum, Soekarno-Hatta International Airport has 5 special programs to support the main health protocols in general, including the Biosecurity Management System, Biosafety Management System, Airport Health Center, Vaccination Center and Workforce Protection. Biosecurity Management System as the main program to strengthen health protocols such as the implementation of 3M, protection for prospective passengers/passengers and airport operational personnel. The Biosafety Management System has a number of programs including biohazard precautions, environment screening, infrastructure sterilization, public health assurance, and presenting laboratory testing facilities for COVID-19 at airports. Airport Health Center, which allows the availability of test services for prospective passengers and the general public. Furthermore, the International Airport also supports the government's program, namely national vaccination through the Vaccination Center at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport. Lastly, Workforce Protection, where this program pays attention to and adjusts operational patterns at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport by digitizing facilities and services, maintaining health for airport operational personnel through 3T. Through this program, Soekarno-Hatta International Airport received an award from the Skytrax Awards as the best airport in terms of health protocols from 38 airports in the world which were considered capable of implementing high standards in health protocols, hygiene, and security protocols in the midst of the global COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, Soekarno-Hatta International Airport has also received recognition from two global institutions, namely the Airport Council International (ACI) and the Safe Travel Barometer. This achievement was achieved due to the synergy between the civil and military apparatus, better known as KOMBATA (Soekarno-Hatta International Airport Community).

2. Synergism between Civilian and Military Apparatuses in Preventing the Transmission of Covid-19 at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport.

Disasters are not only a civilian matter, but require the involvement of the military. Likewise, the handling of Covid-19 in Indonesia does not only involve the government and the general public, but also involves TNI troops. Civil and military coordination in disaster management has been carried out and has been proven to accelerate the handling of disaster management. In the context of a disaster, we can call the relationship between these two actors as civil and military coordination where the main actor or the main control holder is the civilian actor. Civil-military coordination has 3 pillars which include: Humanity, which means protecting victims, especially the most vulnerable; Neutrality, which means that the assistance provided must be neutral without any external elements; and Impartiality,

which means the assistance provided is free from SARA elements. Then, in the coordination between the civil and military apparatus, there are 3 key elements of coordination in disasters and emergencies including: sharing of information (sharing information), Task division (division of tasks), and Planning (planning). When these 3 elements are functioned properly, harmonization and synergism can be created properly

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